

FORMULATION OF A WOOD PRESERVATIVE FROM DIRTY ENGINE OIL

Benedict Nii Ayi Armah
University Of Ghana

Ransford Ganyo
University of Cape Coast, Ghana

ABSTRACT

This study explores the formulation of a wood preservative using waste engine oil as a source of naphthenic acid for synthesizing copper naphthenate. Copper naphthenate is a well-established wood preservative, known for its efficacy against decay fungi, termites, and other wood-destroying organisms. Traditionally, copper naphthenate is synthesized from refined naphthenic acid, a byproduct of petroleum refining. However, limited research has investigated the use of waste engine oil, a readily available and economically feasible alternative, in copper naphthenate production. This study presents a novel approach to repurpose waste engine oil, thereby offering a sustainable and cost-effective solution that addresses waste management challenges in the petroleum industry. The research involved extracting naphthenic acid from waste engine oil through a chemical process using sodium bicarbonate and hydrochloric acid. The extracted acid was then reacted with copper sulfate via a double decomposition method to form copper naphthenate, which was emulsified in diesel fuel to create a wood treatment solution. The resulting formulation was applied to wood samples and assessed over a four-month field trial for its resistance to decay, mold, and termite infestation. Untreated control samples exhibited significant degradation, while treated wood samples demonstrated excellent durability and protection against microbial and insect damage. Analytical techniques, including Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, were used to confirm the composition and purity of the synthesized naphthenic acid. The findings underscore the environmental and economic benefits of utilizing waste engine oil for industrial applications. This approach not only reduces the environmental impact of used engine oil disposal but also provides a low-cost, locally sourced alternative to imported wood preservatives. The study confirms that copper naphthenate synthesized from waste engine oil performs effectively as a wood preservative, meeting industry standards for durability and protection. By contributing to the development of sustainable materials and recycling practices, this work has significant implications for wood preservation industries and supports broader environmental sustainability goals.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Copper naphthenate has been used as a wood preservative since 1889. It was first used in Germany and has been in commercial use since 1911. It was used as a creosote extender during World War II and also given a 5-year ban in the European Union in 2018 (Brient et al., 2020). Creosotes are a type of carbonaceous chemicals that are typically used as preservatives on outside wood structures to prevent rot and fungal attack. Copper naphthenate exhibit a wide range of efficacy against most decay fungi and termites.

Naphthenic acids are a naturally occurring constituents of crude oil that is removed during the manufacture of petroleum products such as diesel fuel, jet fuel and kerosene to improve their technical characteristics (Brient et al., 2020). The removal process generates a waste stream that can be reprocessed to obtain refined naphthenic acids that are useful as wood treatments, corrosion inhibitors, emulsifiers, paint, fuel additives, cutting oils and vinyl stabilizers. Naphthenic acids are extracted from kerosene and diesel streams in the refinery to improve the performance characteristics and storage properties of the finished products (Jechura, 2014). The naphthenic acid streams are known to be wastes from a petroleum industry perspective, however some of the petroleum containing naphthenic acids can be treated to produce refined naphthenic acids which can be used as intermediates in the production of other substances such as wood preservatives.

Naphthenic acid has a high total acid number and also toxic to aquatic algae and other micro-organisms which leads to its characteristic property (Miles et al., 2019). Naphthenic acid molecules possess hydrophilic and hydrophobic functional groups which allow these molecules to penetrate into cell membranes and disrupt cellular function, eventually resulting in cell death. Naphthenic Acid can be acutely toxic to aquatic organisms and to mammals when leached into soil from the wood in to water bodies.

Copper Naphthanate is prepared by reacting copper or copper salts with naphthenic acid or with sodium naphthenate. Copper Naphthenate penetrates the inner part of the wood, provides it with stability and effective against wood-destroying fungi and insects (Jiang et al., 2022).

Reaction of naphthenic acid with copper salt is done by direct metal, metal fusion and double decomposition method. Trade names for copper naphthenate in commercial use includes Type 1 (61% chromium, 22% arsenic and 17% copper) under the trade names Langwood, Green salt and the Type 2 includes (41.5% arsenic, 35.3% chromium and 19.6 % copper) under the trade names Koppers, Osmose K-33 (Sealy, 2022). Other trade names such as CuNap-8, Perm-E8, Cop-R-Nap, Cunapsol and Cuprinol (copper in oil).

In Ghana, used engine oil are disposed or discarded wrongfully having a negative impact on our environment such as polluting water bodies, debris leaching into the soil and destroying plants. Some mechanics and carpenters in Ghana apply used engine oils on woods to prevent decay, this process provides the understanding that the used engine oil exhibits a strong resistance against microorganism such as fungi and bacteria that aids in wood destruction.

Several studies have explored copper naphthenate as a wood preservative, investigating its environmental persistence, efficacy against wood-destroying organisms, and application methods (Fishel, 2018). Research has also addressed copper naphthenate's resistance to leaching, which

makes it suitable for outdoor wood treatments where prolonged exposure to moisture is expected (Sealy, 2022). Meanwhile, studies on wood preservative alternatives, such as borate- and ammonium-based treatments, have highlighted limitations related to environmental leaching and shorter life spans in comparison to copper-based preservatives (Spear, 2015). Recent advancements in sustainable wood preservation have focused on using bio-based treatments; however, these options often lack the efficacy and durability required for long-term protection, especially in areas with heavy fungal or insect activity (Freeman et al., 2013).

While copper naphthenate derived from refined naphthenic acid is commercially available, few studies to the best of our knowledge have examined its synthesis from waste products such as used engine oil. This work specifically addresses this gap by exploring the use of waste engine oil as a source of naphthenic acid in copper naphthenate synthesis. Given the environmental burden of disposing of used engine oil and the growing emphasis on sustainable industrial practices, this approach has both economic and ecological implications. Utilizing waste engine oil could reduce reliance on imported preservatives, lower costs, and provide an effective way to recycle a problematic waste stream.

The objectives of this study are as follows:

- To demonstrate a novel method of synthesizing copper naphthenate from waste engine oil, repurposing its naphthenic acid content for industrial use.
- To evaluate the efficacy of the synthesized copper naphthenate in wood preservation, comparing its performance to traditional sources.
- To promote awareness of the environmental and industrial benefits of recycling waste oil into high-value preservative products.

By addressing this gap, the study provides a new perspective on sustainable wood preservation practices. It not only offers a practical solution to waste management in the petroleum industry but also supports the development of an affordable, locally sourced wood preservative with potential benefits for both the environment and the economy. This work aims to establish copper naphthenate synthesized from waste oil as a viable alternative to imported preservatives, contributing to sustainable innovation in wood treatment.

2.0 Methodology

2.1 Sample Collection

Substantial volume of the dirty oil was collected at a mechanic shop. The sample was transferred into a brown bottle to prevent photo degradation. The bottle was labelled properly and transferred to the laboratory for appropriate analysis.

2.2 Materials and Apparatus

Separatory funnel, Sodium Bicarbonate, Dirty engine Oil, Beaker, Conical flask, Stirring Rod, Concentrated Hydrochloric Acid, Universal Indicator, Oxalic Acid, Phenolphthalein, Diesel Fuel, Copper Sulphate, Wood, Filter paper, Gloves, Nose mask.

Experiment

Substantial volume of the dirty engine oil was filtered to remove particles.

2.3 Dehydration Procedure

100ml of the dirty engine oil was transferred into a 250ml beaker. The beaker was placed on a heating mantle and thermometer was placed into the beaker to record the temperature to 100 -110 degrees Celsius to evaporate water.

2.4 Extraction Procedure

8.535±0.001g of sodium bicarbonate was weighed and transferred into a 100ml volumetric flask. 50ml of the dirty engine oil was transferred into the separatory funnel. Both the sodium bicarbonate and the dirty engine oil were transferred into the 250ml separatory funnel.

The mixture was then rolled gently to ensure that both the spent oil and the sodium bicarbonate had reacted fully. Two layers were obtained and were separated carefully without mixing with each other. The sodium naphthenate (polar) was below and the non-polar was above, The sodium naphthenate obtained was extracted and transferred into a conical flask, 3 to 5 drops of Concentrated HCl was added to the sodium naphthenate to convert to naphthenic acid and make the solution also acidic. A universal indicator was used to determine the pH of the naphthenic acid which had pH of 5.

2.5. Synthesis of Copper Naphthenate

20.040±0.001g of copper sulphate was weighed and transferred into a 250ml beaker and heated for 1 minute, 100ml of naphthenic acid was measured and transferred into the beaker, the mixture was stirred until uniform mixture was obtained. The resulting solution was filtered to obtain the solid copper naphthenate, the copper naphthenate was further washed with water to obtain a pure compound. The wet copper naphthenate was dried to remove every trace of water from the compound. The copper naphthenate weighed was 8.366±0.001g and it was transferred into a sample container. The extraction method was repeated several times.

2.6 FORMATION OF COPPER NAPHTHENATE EMULSION WITH DIESEL FUEL

20.080±0.001g of copper naphthenate was dissolved in 300 ml diesel fuel to obtain 6.66% of copper in copper naphthenate.

2.7 FIELD TRIAL OF COPPER NAPHTHENATE

The copper naphthenate emulsion obtained was applied on wood for a short-term efficacy study of the potency of copper naphthenate as a wood preservative by pressure treatment. The copper naphthenate was applied on the wood by brushing.

3.0 RESULTS

3.1 EFFICACY STUDIES

Short efficacy studies of copper naphthenate on a wood prove to be potent after 4 months of study. Copper naphthenate is known to control decay fungi, molds, termites and wood parasites. Effectiveness against termite, bacteria and fungi was successful after 4 months of Study. The pressure treated wood withstood fungi and bacteria attack, the control wood used could not withstand the attack from fungi and bacteria.

AFTER FOUR MONTHS – TREATED WOOD

Figure 1: First Stage

Figure 2: Second Stage

Figure 3: Third Stage

After Four Months-Control Wood

Figure 4: First Stage

Figure 5: Second Stage

3.2 Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Results

Naphthenic acid after extraction substantial amount of the extract was used to run nuclear magnetic resonance (^1H NMR).

Figure 6: Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Results

3.3 Reference Nuclear Magnetic Resonance

^1H of naphthenic acid

^1H of naphthenic acid

Pulse Sequence: s2pu1

^{13}C NMR of naphthenic acid

Merichen Nap.Acids-approx.100mg/mL
Pulse Sequence: zgpg30

4.0 CONCLUSION

Short efficacy studies of copper naphthenate on the wood prove to be potent after four months of study, the wood withstood fungi and bacteria attack. The control mango wood used could not withstand the attack from fungi and bacteria attack, it further led to the decay of the wood.

Nuclear magnetic resonance experiments showed no evidence of carboxylic acid this might be due to the low concentrations of naphthenic acid present in the extract. There was also a possibility of naphthenic acids being modified to some other acid derivatives during the extraction process. The implications of engine oil on the environment however merit further research and its applications as wood preservative.

4.1 RECOMMENDATION

Based on the key findings that emerge from the study and the conclusions drawn, the following recommendations are made.

- A comprehensive study should be conducted on the same topic on a larger sample size and solvent extraction process.
- The use of water-based wood preservatives that is less toxic than oil-based preservatives.

REFERENCES

- Brient, J. A., Manning, M. J., & Freeman, M. H. (2020). Copper naphthenate - protecting America's infrastructure for over 100 years and its potential for expanded use in Canada and Europe. *Wood Material Science and Engineering*, 15(6), 368–376.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/17480272.2020.1837948>
- Fishel, F. M. (2018). *Wood Preservatives 1*.
- Freeman, M. H., Kitchens, S. C., & Amburgey, T. L. (2013). Wood Preservative Systems Containing Copper and Borates: Efficacy and Synergy. In *AMERICAN WOOD PROTECTION ASSOCIATION* (Issue Lloyd 1990, pp. 226–240).
<https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5b354bd6f8370a13b49308c4/t/5bb3937c71c10b1f16f34496/1538495370404/Wood+Preservative+Systems+Containing+Copper+and+Borates+Efficacy+and+Synergy.pdf>
- Jechura, J. (2014). *Refinery Feedstocks & Products – Properties & Specifications*.
- Jiang, J., Han, S., Ren, X., Wang, H., Yu, H., & Sun, F. (2022). Enhanced durability of round bamboo treated with copper naphthenate under heat-cold impregnation. *Royal Society Open Science*, 9(11). <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.220247>
- Miles, S. M., Hofstetter, S., Edwards, T., Dlusskaya, E., Cologgi, D. L., Gänzle, M., & Ulrich, A. C. (2019). Tolerance and cytotoxicity of naphthenic acids on microorganisms isolated from oil sands process-affected water. *Science of the Total Environment*, 695, 133749.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.133749>
- Sealy, E. A. (2022). The Treatment of Wood (Lumber)-2% Copper Naphthenate in Kerosene a Treatment for Decay Fungi, Insects-Termites, Ants and Beetles. *Scholars Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 10(8), 185–205.
<https://doi.org/10.36347/sjet.2022.v10i08.001>
- Spear, M. J. (2015). Preservation, protection and modification of wood composites. In *Wood Composites*. Elsevier Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-1-78242-454-3.00011-1>
- Brient, J. A., Manning, M. J., & Freeman, M. H. (2020). Copper naphthenate - protecting America's infrastructure for over 100 years and its potential for expanded use in Canada and Europe. *Wood Material Science and Engineering*, 15(6), 368–376.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/17480272.2020.1837948>
- Fishel, F. M. (2018). *Wood Preservatives 1*.
- Freeman, M. H., Kitchens, S. C., & Amburgey, T. L. (2013). Wood Preservative Systems Containing Copper and Borates: Efficacy and Synergy. In *AMERICAN WOOD PROTECTION ASSOCIATION* (Issue Lloyd 1990, pp. 226–240).
<https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5b354bd6f8370a13b49308c4/t/5bb3937c71c10b1f16f34496/1538495370404/Wood+Preservative+Systems+Containing+Copper+and+Borates+Efficacy+and+Synergy.pdf>
- Jechura, J. (2014). *Refinery Feedstocks & Products – Properties & Specifications*.

- Jiang, J., Han, S., Ren, X., Wang, H., Yu, H., & Sun, F. (2022). Enhanced durability of round bamboo treated with copper naphthenate under heat-cold impregnation. *Royal Society Open Science*, 9(11). <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.220247>
- Miles, S. M., Hofstetter, S., Edwards, T., Dlusskaya, E., Cologgi, D. L., Gänzle, M., & Ulrich, A. C. (2019). Tolerance and cytotoxicity of naphthenic acids on microorganisms isolated from oil sands process-affected water. *Science of the Total Environment*, 695, 133749. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.133749>
- Sealy, E. A. (2022). The Treatment of Wood (Lumber)-2% Copper Naphthenate in Kerosene a Treatment for Decay Fungi, Insects-Termites, Ants and Beetles. *Scholars Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 10(8), 185–205. <https://doi.org/10.36347/sjet.2022.v10i08.001>
- Spear, M. J. (2015). Preservation, protection and modification of wood composites. In *Wood Composites*. Elsevier Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-1-78242-454-3.00011-1>